

New European Bauhaus Call for proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities

Project Acronym: SOCIAL4FOOD

**Project title: SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge
transfer and production of typical local FOOD**

Deliverable 4.1: RESULTS OF THE SOCIAL4FOOD TRAINING ACTIVITIES

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1. Executive summary

The SOCIAL4FOOD project aims to apply the New European Bauhaus principles to improve the contact between young generations and green public spaces, guided by the wisdom of the elders. Through a series of social farming activities, the project aims to stimulate the involvement of teenagers from the Town of Arsoli (including also young immigrants) in collaboratively farming and cooking a very ancient and high-quality bean typical of this town, named “fagiolina arsolana”.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive description of the results of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (Green social laboratories, SOCIAL4FOOD competition, co-design of the social farm) that were organized in Arsoli (RM). Specifically, the green social laboratories took place on August 18, 2022, and September 24, 2022, the SOCIAL4FOOD competition on September 4, 2022, and the first and second events of the co-design of the social farm on July 29, 2022, and September 24, 2022. These events constitute the second phase of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach. Five different target groups of participants including local teenagers, local children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens, were involved in an attempt to transfer the knowledge on how to grow and cook the “fagiolina arsolana” from elders to the young generation.

The SOCIAL4FOOD training activities contribute in:

- *handing down the experience and skill needed to grow and traditionally cook this local product from local elders to teenagers by stimulating the development of their talents;*
- *strengthening the sense of belonging to the community by organizing a local competition aimed to test the cooking skills of citizens in preparing a creative recipe of the “fagiolina”;*
- *promoting health by offering areas for physical activities, stress relief, social interaction, and inclusion (mainly disadvantaged people).*

2. The applied methodology

During the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities, the second stage (ideate and prototype) of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach, as described in Deliverable 3.1, was applied. Local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, and farmers were involved in the transfer of knowledge on how to grow and cook the “fagiolina arsolana” and put into practice what they learned.

During this second stage, “learning by doing” was applied, which is an educational approach expounded by Paulo Freire (1982). It is a hands-on approach to learning in which participants interact with their environment and actually “do” the activity to adapt and learn. The learning-by-doing approach is composed of the following four phases (see Figure 1), as defined by Kolb (1984): (1) having a concrete experience followed by (2) observation of and reflection on that experience which leads to (3) the formation of abstract concepts (analysis) and generalizations (conclusions) which are then (4) used to test a hypothesis in future situations, resulting in new experiences.

Figure 1: The phases of the learning-by-doing approach followed in the SOCIAL4FOOD project

A brief description of each phase is provided below.

Concrete Experience

This activity started with the knowledge transfer of cultivation techniques/cooking recipes of the “fagiolina arsolana” from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques.

Participants learned about the experience told by the elderly and local farmers watching

them in action. To acquire new knowledge, participants were actively engaged in cultivation/cooking activities.

Reflective Observation

This phase in the learning cycle allowed participants to discuss the experience with others. Participants were divided into groups and were invited to discuss their concrete experiences by highlighting the difficulties and the necessary improvements in the acquired knowledge.

Abstract Conceptualization

In this phase, participants moved from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization by classifying concepts and forming conclusions on the experience. They were asked to take notes about the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (experience notes).

Active Experimentation

This stage in the cycle is the testing stage. Participants had a new cultivation/cooking experience in which they applied the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (written in their experience notes).

2.1. GREEN SOCIAL LABORATORIES

Three different green social laboratories (i.e., "I learn how to grow the fagiolina", "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", and "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina") were held by local elders and producers to transfer to adolescents, children, and interested citizens their knowledge on:

- the cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the cooking of local recipes of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana".

In these laboratories, the first, second, and third phases (i.e., concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization) of the learning-by-doing approach are implemented.

2.2. SOCIAL4FOOD COMPETITION

A culinary challenge was held during the "fagiolina festival" involving several groups composed of participants in the green social laboratories who tried their hand at cooking typical recipes.

In this competition, the last phase (i.e., active experimentation) of the learning-by-doing approach was implemented.

2.3. CO-CREATION OF THE SOCIAL FARM

Starting from the needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm gathered during the Open Day event organized on July 29th, 2022, two further events for the co-creation of the social farm have been organized.

During the second co-creation event held on September 24th, 2022 each participant was asked to provide some solutions about the organization of the social farm, people to involve, and tasks to perform. Then, through a collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the social farm has been provided. Moreover, a group of “Fagiolina Ambassadors” has been appointed to stimulate citizen and stakeholder engagement and participation. For the appointment, representatives for each target group involved in the project (teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens) have been selected according to their commitment to the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.

During the third co-creation event held on October 29th, 2022, the shared solution about the organization of the social farm emerged during the second co-creation event (specifically people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.) has been illustrated to representatives of the four entities responsible for the management of the social farm in the coming years (the Municipality of Arsoli, Pro Loco of Arsoli, Social elderly center of Arsoli and local farmers of the association “Amici della fagiolina arsolana”). A preliminary version of a collaboration agreement (provided in appendix A) containing the activities for the management of the social farm, as emerged during the second co-creation event, which each entity is responsible for, has been discussed.

3. Obtained results

The SOCIAL4FOOD training activities were attended by 102 people, to which 16 people (non-overlapping to people participating in the training activities) have to be added attending the first step of the co-creation of the social farm held during the Open day event held on July 29, 2022. Therefore, the total number of participants was 118 people, belonging to the target groups described in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Target groups that attended the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities

Considering the gender dimension of the participants, the event was attended by 77 women (65%) and 41 men (35%), as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Gender of participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities

In this section, the results of the different events organized during the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (Green social laboratories, SOCIAL4FOOD competition, co-design of the social farm) are described in detail.

3.1. Results of the Green social laboratories

The Green social laboratories were attended by 82 people belonging to the target groups described in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Target groups that attended the Green social laboratories

Considering the gender dimension of the participants, the event was attended by 55 women (67%) and 27 men (33%), as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Gender of participants in the Green social laboratories

In the following paragraphs, the results obtained in the different phases of the applied methodology, described in Section 2, are provided for each laboratory ("I learn how to grow the fagiolina", "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", and "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina").

3.1.1. Results of the Laboratory "I learn how to grow the fagiolina"

During the first laboratory "I learn how to grow the fagiolina", the first, second, and third stages of the learning-by-doing methodology were applied, as described in the following paragraphs.

Concrete Experience

This activity started with the knowledge transfer of cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana" from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques. Participants were divided into 2 groups, each own followed by a local farmer, who illustrated the different phases of the growing process. Participants were actively engaged in cultivation activities, as illustrated in the photos provided in the following paragraphs divided for each phase of the growing process.

Land preparation

Sowing

Covering the seeds

Building of the "conocchie" (support scaffold for the growth of the plant)

Reflective Observation

In this phase, the 2 groups of participants were invited to discuss their concrete experiences by highlighting the difficulties and the necessary improvements in the acquired knowledge. Some photos of this phase are provided below.

From the analysis of the discussions, the participants highlighted the following difficulties: sticking the "conocchie" into the ground, high effort, difficulties in the use of the hoe, and in general all the tools necessary for sowing the bean. On the contrary, they expressed the following positive aspects: the contact with nature, having learned the Arsoli culture, the use of agricultural tools, having learned the cultivation of the bean which is a typical product of Arsoli, and digital detox.

Abstract Conceptualization

In this phase, participants moved from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization by classifying concepts and forming conclusions on the experience. They were asked to take notes about the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (experience notes). Some photos of the experience notes written by participants are shown below.

- ARATURA
 - FRESATURA
 - SOLCATURA (distanza: 100 cm da un suono e l'altro) USARE ZAPPA
 - X SOCHI dritti → PALI CON FIDU
 - SEMINA → TUBO DI PLASTICA dove si SEMINANO I Fagioli stando in piedi: se ne piantano 5
 a distanza di 40-50 cm di distanza. Fagioli ricoperti con la terra.
 - SARCHIATURA = ZAPPARE LA PIANTA e creare canale di irrigazione
 - CONOCCHIATURA: si usano le corna come sostegno x la PIANTA che si ARATURA con le CORNE
 - INNAFFIATURA → IN BASE AL TERRENO
 - RACCOLTA = LA Fagiolina e' secca

DIFFICOLTA'
 - UTILIZZO ZAPPA
 - FATICA FISICA

ASPETTI POSITIVI
 IMPARARE LA CULTURA ARSOCANA E
 A USARE GLI ATTREZZI AGRICOLI

DIARIO di VIAGGIO di CAMILLA

ARATURA DEL TERRENO
- FRESATURA DEL TERRENO
- SOLCATURA (Distanza 60 cm)
SOLCO FATTO CON CANNUCCE, FIDIO E ZAPPA
PER PANTARE I FAGIOLI ABBIAMO USATO UN TUBO PER NON CURVARCI. (SEMINA) IN ~~OGNI~~ OGNI BUCA CIRCA 5 FAGIOLI -
SOLCO PROFONDO 30 CM.
I SEMI VENGONO RICOPERTI CON LA TERRA.
- SI ASPETTA CHE LA PIANTINA CRESCA UN PO' SENZA FARE LE CORDE (SARCHIATURA) E ZAPPARE LA PIANTINA. ~~VIENE~~ VIENE CREATO IL CANALE PER FAR SCORRERE L'ACQUA
- CONOCCHIATURA = 4 PALI ATTACCATI TRA LORO PER FAR CRESCERE LE CORDE DELLA PIANTA

DIFFICOLTA' INFILARE LE CANNE NEL TERRENO

FATICA FISICA C'ERA TROPPO SOLE PERCIO' HO SODATO BASTISSIMO

ASPETTI POSITIVI STARE NELLA NATURA ED AVERE IMPARATO UNA NUOVA CULTURA

DIARIO DI VIAGGIO
DI :

ARATURA TERRENO
- FRESATURA TERRENO
= SOLCATURA dis. 60 CM
- PER FARE IL SOLCO DRITTO ABBIAMO USATO LA ZAPPA
+ SEMINA: SI PRENDE UN TUBO CHE SERVE A SEMINARE I FAGIOLI SENZA FATICA DI FAGIOLI SE NE PANTANO 5 A DISTANZA DI 40 o 50 CM.
- RICOPERTA DEI SEMI CON LA TERRA SCAVATA
- "SARCHIATURA": ~~È~~ È ZAPPARE LA PIANTINA E CREARE IL CANALE PER L'IRRIGAZIONE
- "CONOCCHIATURA": LE "CONOCCHIE" SONO DEI CANNE CHE SERVONO PER FAR CRESCERE E FAR ARRAMPICARE LA FAGIOLINA
DIFFICOLTA': METTERE LE CANNE

1) ARATURA TERRENO
2) FRESATURA il terreno viene reso morbido e fino attraverso il uso di macchinari oppure
3) SOLCATURA: vengono fatti dei solchi a distanza ~~di~~ di 60 cm tra di loro
4) SEMINA: vengono piantati i fagioli (5/6 fagioli) attraverso il uso di un tubo per evitare di stare sempre curvati ~~stare~~ vengono ~~piantati~~ ^{piantati} circa 40-50 cm. Successivamente i solchi vengono coperti
5) "SARCHIATURA" viene "zappata" la feccia pianta per consentire la necrosi mistrofitica

6) "CONOCCHIATURA", le corde di fieno vengono utilizzate e fissate da supporti (tutor) alla uscita della fogeduna. Ogni corde puo' essere piantata in ogni punto che si vuole compiere in dolce attorno alla corde
Le forni successive sono l'irrigazione delle piante e la raccolta della fogeduna (foce finale) che avviene quando il fopedo e' secco (da settembre e ottobre)
• DIFFICOLTA' Utilizzo delle zappa ed il periodo degli ottimi raccolti puo' la tenuta delle fogeduna

3.1.2. Results of the Laboratory "I learn how to cook the fagiolina"

During the second laboratory "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", the first, second, and third stages of the learning-by-doing methodology were applied, as described in the following paragraphs.

Concrete Experience

This activity started with the knowledge transfer of a typical recipe (i.e. “ciciarchiole”) with the “fagiolina arsolana” from the local elderly ladies to participants using storytelling techniques. Participants were followed by local elderly ladies, who illustrated the different phases of the cooking process. Participants were actively engaged in cooking activities, as illustrated in the photos provided in the following paragraphs divided for each phase of the cooking process.

Preparation of the sauce

Preparation of the hand-made pasta

Final baking

Reflective Observation

In this phase, participants were divided into several groups and were invited to discuss their concrete experiences by highlighting the difficulties and the necessary improvements in the acquired knowledge. Some photos of this phase are provided below.

From the analysis of the discussions, the participants highlighted as positive aspects, the fun and the positive experience of observing and learning the procedure for the preparation of the sauce and the hand-made pasta. No difficulties were highlighted by participants.

Abstract Conceptualization

In this phase, participants moved from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization by classifying concepts and forming conclusions on the experience. They were asked to take notes about the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (experience notes). Some photos of the experience notes written by participants are shown below.

1) ABBIAMO FATTO IL SUGO CON IL SEDANO, LA CIPOLLA, LA PANCETTA, TANTO OLIO E LE CAROTE.

2) ABBIAMO FATTO LA FONTANA CON LA FARINA E CI ABBIAMO MESSO DENTRO L'UOVO E MA N' HANNO L'ACQUA. ABBIAMO IMPASTATO FINCHE' LA PASTA NON E' DIVENTATA BELLA DURA.

3) ABBIAMO FATTO UNA BELLA SFOGLIA ROTONDA

4) ABBIAMO ARROTOLATO LA SFOGLIA E L'ABBIAMO TAGLIATA PRIMA A RIGHE E POI A QUADRETTI.

5) L'ABBIAMO COTTE.

6) CE LE SIANO MANGIATE.

DIARIO DI VIAGGIO DI
Gina [redacted]

IL DIARIO DI DAMIANO MAGNANI

1 ABBIAMO FATTO IL SUGO CON L'OLIO LA PANCETTA LA CIPOLLA IL SEDANO

2 ABBIAMO MESSO LA FARINA A FONTANA ABBIAMO AGGIUNTO L'UOVO E ABBIAMO IMPASTATO

3 ABBIAMO FATTO LA SFOGLIA ROTONDA L'ANNATAIATA

4 LA STANNO CUOCENDO

SUGO (PROCEDIMENTO)

1. PRENDERE UNA PENTOLA
2. AGGIUNGERE L'OLIO NELLA PENTOLA
3. METTERE LA PANCETTA
4. AGGIUNGERE IL SEDANO
5. METTERE LA CAROTA
6. AGGIUNGERE LA CIPOLLA
7. METTERE LA PASTATA DI POMODORO
8. E FARLO BOLLIRE

CILIA RICHIOLE (PROCEDIMENTO)

1. PRENDERE LA FARINA
2. METTERE LA FARINA SUL TAVOLO
3. E AGGIUNGERE L'UOVO ALLA FARINA
4. AMALGAMARE IL TUTTO
5. STENDERE L'IMPASTO
6. TAGLIARLO A CUBETTI
7. E METTERLO IN PENTOLA

DIARIO DI VIAGGIO DI ROBERTO ZASI

FASE 1: METTERE L'OLIO

FASE 2: METTERE UNA CAROTA

FASE 3: METTERE LA CIPOLLA

FASE 4: METTERE IL SUGO DI POMODORO

FASE 5: METTERE LA PANCETTA

FASE 6: METTERE LA VENTRESCA.

IL DIARIO DI DARIO AMICI

1. PRODUCIMENTO DEL SUGO. SUGO PANCETTA CAROTTA SEDANO LA CIPOLLA METTERE L'OLIO
2. LA FONTANELLA DI FARINA
3. L'UOVO E DOPO IMPASTATO
4. HO CREATO LA PALLETTA
5. LO STESA
6. PINA LA TAGLIATA LA PASTA HA QUADRATINI
7. LE SIGNORE STANO CUOCENDO
8. CE LE MANGIAMO TUTTE.

IL PRIMO RUDOVICO CAUCCI

1. PRODUCIMENTO DEL SUGO PANCETTA CIPOLLA CAROTE SEDANO E L'OLIO
2. LA FONTANELLA DELLA FARINA
3. L'UOVO E ABBIAMO IMPASTATO
4. HO CREATO UNA PALLETTA
5. HO STESO LA PALLETTA
6. PINA HA TAGLIATO LA PALLETTA E HA FATTO LA ORBICOLE
7. LE SIGNORE ORA STANNO CUOCENDO
8. E FINALMENTE LE MANGIAMO

① ABBIAMO MESSO UOVA, FARINA, ACQUA E ABBIAMO MESCOLATO

② ABBIAMO IMPASTATO E FORMATO UNA PALLA

③ ABBIAMO STESO LA PASTA CON IL MATTARELLO

④ QUANDO È DIVENTATA ASCIUTTA ABBIAMO PIEGATO LA PASTA E L'ABBIAMO TAGLIATA A QUADRETTI

SUGO

- SI SOFFRIGGONO CAROTA, CIPOLLA E SEDANO E PANCETTA
- POI SI AGGIUNGE IL POMODORO
- DOPO SI BUTTANO DENTRO I FAGIOLI GIÀ COTTI

MI SONO DIVERTITA TANTISSIMO

DIARIO DI VIAGGIO DI ADELE DESANTIS

DIARIO DI PETRA PIZZENTINI

- 1- ABBIAMO SOFFRITTO LA CAROTA, LA CIPOLLA E IL SEDANO
- 2- ABBIAMO AGGIUNTO LA PANCETTA E IL POMODORO
- 3- ABBIAMO FATTO CUOCERE IL SUGO
- 4- POI ABBIAMO PRESO LA FARINA E CI ABBIAMO FATTO LA FONTANELLA E POI ABBIAMO MESSO L'ACQUA E L'UOVO
- 5- ABBIAMO IMPASTATO TUTTO
- 6- ABBIAMO STESO L'IMPASTO
- 7- L'ABBIAMO PIEGATO E TAGLIATO
- 8- ABBIAMO FATTO LE CICIARCHIOLU
- 9- ADDESSO LE SIGNORE LE CUOCERANNO E LE MANGHERANNO

♥ PETRA

DIARIO DI CARLOTTA NARDONI

PER CUOCERE LE CICIARCHIOLU ABBIAMO PREPARATO IL SUGO CON SEDANO CAROTA CIPOLLA E IL POMODORO POI ABBIAMO PREPARATO L'IMPASTO CON FARINA UOVA E ACQUA ABBIAMO STESO LA SFOGLIA CON IL MATTARELLO POI ABBIAMO TAGLIATO LA SFOGLIA IN TANTI PEZZETTI QUADRETTI CHE POI VERRANNO COTTI E NOI CE LI MANGIAMO

18/08/2022

DIARIO DI COSTANZA BORGHI

MI È PIACIUTO:

- IMPASTARE
- VERERE COME SI FA IL SUGO
- VERERE COME SI FANNO LE CICIARCHIOLU.
- E LA COTURA.

GRAZIE PER L'ATTIVITÀ SVOLTA.

COSTANZA BORGHI

♥

3.1.3. Results of the Laboratory "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina"

During the third laboratory "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina", the first, second, and third stages of the learning-by-doing methodology were applied, as described in the following paragraphs.

Concrete Experience

This activity started with the knowledge transfer of harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana" from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques. Local farmers illustrated the different phases of the harvesting process. Participants were actively engaged in harvesting activities, as illustrated in the photos provided below.

Reflective Observation

In this phase, participants were invited to discuss their concrete experiences by highlighting the difficulties in the acquired knowledge. Some photos of this phase are provided below.

Abstract Conceptualization

In this phase, participants moved from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization by classifying concepts and forming conclusions on the experience. They were asked to take notes about the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (experience notes). Some photos of the experience notes written by participants are shown below.

3.2. Results of the SOCIAL4FOOD Competition

The SOCIAL4FOOD Competition was attended by 34 people belonging to the target groups described in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Target groups that attended the SOCIAL4FOOD Competition

Considering the gender dimension of the participants, the event was attended by 22 women (65%) and 12 men (35%), as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 7: Gender of participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD Competition

The culinary challenge consisted of a competition in the creation of a typical local recipe named “ciciarchiole” (i.e. hand-made pasta with a sauce prepared using the fagiolina arsolana) following the instructions learned during the laboratory “I learn how to cook the fagiolina” held on August 18, 2022. Five heterogeneous groups (adults and children) composed of 6 participants have been created. The ingredients for the preparation of pasta and sauce, a pastry board, a rolling pin, and an electric stove for the cooking were provided to each group. A couple of hours have been given to make the recipe. A jury composed of 3 people evaluated the recipes realized by each group and declared the winner. Some photos of the event are shown below.

3.3. Results of the second co-creation event of the social farm

The second step of the co-creation of the social farm was attended by 19 people belonging to the target groups described in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Target groups that attended the second event of co-creation of the social farm

Considering the gender dimension of the participants, the event was attended by 7 women (37%) and 12 men (63%), as illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Gender of participants in the second event of co-creation of the social farm

Starting from the needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm gathered during the Open Day event organized on July 29th, 2022, each participant was asked to fill out a questionnaire to provide some solutions about the organization of the social farm, people to involve, and tasks to perform. In particular, a short questionnaire (see Appendix A) aimed to deepen the third triggering question submitted to participants during the Open day event (i.e. How would you like to organize the social farm? Who should be involved? How should the tasks be performed?). Note that not all participants filled out the questionnaire and not all participants answered all the questions of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was composed of 4 multiple-choice questions and an open-ended space where respondents

were able to add comments or suggestions in the form of text. The options available for each multiple-choice question have been defined according to the most common idea voted by the various groups of participants in the open-day event (for more detail see Figure 9 of Del 2.2). Afterward, through a collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the social farm has been provided. In the following subsections, the results of the questionnaire and the collaborative discussion are illustrated.

3.3.1 Results of the questionnaire

Considering the first question of the questionnaire (i.e., How would you like the social farm to be organized for the cultivation of the “fagiolina arsolana”?) participants could choose between two options. Pros and cons have been also underlined by participants as shown in Table 1

Available options	The number of participants who selected this option	Pro	Cons
Establishment of a small social cooperative that can use its resources in the cultivation of all local products	1	More cooperation among involved people	Social cooperatives require too much bureaucracy and demand from the involved people
Creation of cultivation groups of volunteers who take care of a parcel of state-owned land	7	More freedom and autonomy of choice It can represent the first solution to which the establishment of the small social cooperative follows	

One participant suggested (within the open-ended space) restoring abandoned lands allowing everyone to cultivate them.

For the second question of the questionnaire (i.e., Who should be involved?) participants could choose between seven options as shown in Table 2. Participants have been also asked to indicate the name of people for each selected option.

Available options	The number of participants who selected this option
Local agricultural associations	6
Elderly people	3
Young	4

Local associations	3
Unemployed who want to get involved and work in the countryside	4
Disabled people	1
Young people who are not busy with school during the summer	3

For the third question of the questionnaire (i.e., How should the tasks to be performed be defined?) participants could choose between four options as shown in Table 3. Participants have been also asked to indicate the name of people to involve in the different tasks to perform such as Social farm coordination, soil preparation, sowing, care and maintenance, and harvest.

Available options	The number of participants who selected this option
The most experienced people should have the responsibility of organizing the social garden	3
The main role must be given to the producer who has the most experience	2
Local associations guide the younger generations also through the experience of the elderly	4
All participants are involved in the various operational phases	3

Finally for the fourth question (i.e., How could the harvest be exploited?) participants could choose between two options. One pro has been also underlined by participants as shown in Table 4

Available options	The number of participants who selected this option	Pro
The revenue should be used during the bean festival	0	Allows producers to increase production
The revenue should be used for the purchase of agricultural equipment to improve and expand the cultivation of the “fagiolina arsolana” in the following years	6	

One participant suggested (within the open-ended space) using the revenue to purchase other lands for the cultivation of the “fagiolina arsolana”

Some photos of participants filling in the questionnaire are shown below.

3.3.2 Results of the collaborative discussion

During the collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the social farm has been defined that confirmed the results of the questionnaire. Specifically, participants confirmed the need to create cultivation groups of volunteers who take care of a parcel of state-owned land to avoid bureaucratic constraints, also the target groups to involve have been confirmed in particular the local agricultural associations, elderly people, young, local associations, unemployed who want to get involved and work in the countryside and young people who are not busy with school during the summer. Concerning tasks to be performed all the options have been selected. Finally, participants confirmed the choice to use the revenue for the purchase of agricultural equipment to improve and expand the cultivation of the “fagiolina arsolana” in the following years

Some photos of the collaborative discussion are shown below.

A group of “Fagiolina Ambassadors” has been appointed to stimulate citizen and stakeholder engagement and participation. For the appointment, representatives for each target group involved in the project (teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens) have been selected according to their commitment to the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities. A photo of the ambassadors is shown below.

3.4. Results of the third co-creation event of the social farm

The third step of the co-creation of the social farm was attended by 8 people belonging to the target groups described in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Target groups that attended the third event of co-creation of the social farm

Considering the gender dimension of the participants, the event was attended by 6 women (75%) and 2 men (25%), as illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Gender of participants in the third event of co-creation of the social farm

During the third co-creation event held on October 29th, 2022, the shared solution about the organization of the social farm emerged during the second co-creation event (specifically people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.) has been illustrated to representatives of the four entities responsible for the management of the social farm in the coming years (the Municipality of Arsoli, Pro Loco of Arsoli, Social elderly center of Arsoli and local farmers of the association “Amici della fagiolina arsolana”). A preliminary version of a collaboration agreement (provided in appendix A) containing the activities for the management of the social farm, as emerged during the second co-creation event, which each entity is responsible for has been discussed.

Some photos of the collaborative discussion are shown below.

Appendix A

ACCORDO di COLLABORAZIONE

TRA

COMUNE di Arsoli, con sede a Arsoli in Piazza dei Martiri Antifascisti n.3, rappresentato agli effetti del presente atto dal Sindaco, Sig. Gabriele Caucci;

E

CENTRO SOCIALE ANZIANI di Arsoli, con sede a Arsoli in Via Dei Massimo n. 68, rappresentato agli effetti del presente atto dal Presidente, Sig. Fabrizio Proietti;

E

PRO LOCO di Arsoli, con sede a Arsoli in Piazza Amico d'Arsoli n. 13 rappresentato agli effetti del presente atto dal Presidente, Arch. Chiara Bruni;

E

Associazione Amici della Fagiolina Arsolana, con sede a Arsoli in Piazza Amico D'Arsoli n. 1, rappresentato agli effetti del presente atto dal Presidente, Sig. Pietro Cerroni.

PREMESSO

- Visto lo Statuto del Comune di Arsoli;
- Visto lo Statuto del Centro sociale anziani di Arsoli;
- Visto lo Statuto della Pro Loco di Arsoli;
- Visto lo Statuto dell'Associazione Amici della Fagiolina Arsolana;
- Considerato che le Parti intendono collaborare nel garantire il mantenimento dell'orto sociale predisposto nell'ambito del Progetto SOCIAL4FOOD (SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge transfer and production of typical local FOOD), coordinato dal Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche-IRPPS e finanziato dall'Istituto Europeo di Innovazione e Tecnologia nell'ambito del bando "EIT Community New European Bauhaus Call for Proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities".

Tutto ciò premesso e considerato,

SI CONVIENE E SI STIPULA QUANTO SEGUE

Art. 1 - Premesse

Le premesse costituiscono parte integrante del presente Accordo di collaborazione e si considerano integralmente riportate nel presente articolo.

Art. 2 - Disciplina dei rapporti tra le Parti

2.1. Le Parti dichiarano che intendono regolare i loro rapporti nel rispetto della vigente normativa e, di conseguenza, si impegnano all'osservanza di quanto previsto nel presente Accordo e in tutti gli atti da essa derivanti o ad essa riconducibili.

2.2. Le Parti concorderanno, ove necessario, gli adeguamenti del presente Accordo alle disposizioni di carattere innovativo o integrativo dei rispettivi Statuti e Regolamenti. Tali adeguamenti troveranno formalizzazione mediante atto aggiuntivo con le medesime procedure di perfezionamento del presente Accordo.

Art. 3 - Oggetto dell'Accordo

- 3.1. Il presente Accordo ha come oggetto la definizione dell'ambito di collaborazione tra le Parti finalizzata alla divulgazione dei risultati del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD e all'organizzazione di eventi per stimolare la partecipazione della cittadinanza arsolana alle attività di mantenimento dell'orto sociale.
- 3.2. Le attività potranno essere attivate presso le rispettive sedi coinvolgendo risorse umane e attrezzature di tutte le Parti.
- 3.3. La cooperazione tra le Parti è ispirata al principio di reciprocità ed equa distribuzione degli eventuali oneri annessi.

Art. 4 - Impegni delle Parti e Nomina dei responsabili

- 4.1. Ai fini dell'attuazione dell'Accordo, le Parti d'intesa individuano quali referenti il/la Sig/Sig.ra per il Centro Sociale Anziani, il/la Sig/Sig.ra per la Pro Loco di Arsoli e il/la Sig/Sig.ra xxxxxxxxxx per l'Associazione Amici della Fagiolina Arsolana, che assumono il compito di curare e coordinare i rapporti tra i due Enti per la realizzazione delle attività di interesse comune.
- 4.2. Ciascuna Parte potrà, su richiesta dell'altra e nelle forme previste e consentite dalle normative legislative e regolamentari, autorizzare i propri membri/soci/personale a partecipare ad attività che si svolgono presso le strutture delle altre Parti e ciò al fine di svolgere congiuntamente le attività di cui all'art. 3.
- 4.3. La Pro Loco di Arsoli, in collaborazione con il Centro Sociale Anziani di Arsoli, organizzerà annualmente (orientativamente nei mesi di Agosto o Settembre) il laboratorio di cucina "Co' pigne e stenneregli: impariamo a cucinare la fagiolina".
- 4.4. La Pro Loco di Arsoli, in collaborazione con l'Associazione Amici della Fagiolina Arsolana, organizzerà annualmente (orientativamente nei mesi di Luglio, Agosto o Settembre) presso l'orto sociale i laboratori sulle tecniche di coltivazione e raccolta dal titolo "Tu lo sa che so' le conocchie?: impariamo a coltivare la fagiolina" e "Dalle conocchie ai pannuni: impariamo a raccogliere la fagiolina" (in cui i bambini e adolescenti contribuiranno alla raccolta del prodotto).
- 4.5. L'Associazione Amici della Fagiolina Arsolana, in collaborazione con la Pro Loco di Arsoli, organizzerà annualmente (orientativamente nel mese di Maggio) un evento didattico sulla semina della Fagiolina Arsolana presso l'orto sociale (in cui i bambini e adolescenti contribuiranno alla semina del prodotto).
- 4.6. Il Centro Sociale Anziani di Arsoli, in collaborazione con l'Associazione Amici della Fagiolina Arsolana e la Pro Loco di Arsoli, si occuperanno del mantenimento dell'orto sociale (in particolare dell'annaffiatura e della cura della piantagione) nel periodo estivo (da Giugno a Settembre) coinvolgendo i bambini e gli adolescenti arsolani.
- 4.7. Il Comune di Arsoli, in collaborazione con l'Associazione Amici della Fagiolina Arsolana, si occuperà annualmente (orientativamente nel mese di Aprile) dell'aratura e fresatura del terreno.

Art. 5 - Decorrenza e Durata dell'Accordo

- 5.1. Il presente Accordo ha una durata di tre anni a decorrere dalla conclusione del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD in data 30/11/2022 e potrà essere rinnovato per un uguale periodo tramite comunicazione scritta tra le parti.
- 5.2. Il recesso da tale Accordo, consentito in qualsiasi momento, dovrà essere comunicato con preavviso scritto di almeno trenta giorni, fermo restando l'obbligo, salvo comune diverso avviso formalizzato per iscritto, di adempimento degli impegni già assunti, nel rispetto

comunque del presente articolato, che conserverà in ogni caso piena efficacia fino al completamento di tutte le attività svolte in cooperazione ai sensi del presente Accordo.

Art. 6 – Divulgazione, Spese di gestione e Utilizzazione del ricavato

6.1. Le Parti convengono sul comune interesse alla valorizzazione dell'immagine di ciascuna di esse nelle comunicazioni all'esterno relative a sviluppi e risultati dell'attività oggetto del presente Accordo.

6.2. Le Parti si autorizzano reciprocamente a rendere note, sui rispettivi siti istituzionali, la partnership oggetto del presente Accordo e a pubblicare sul medesimo sito, salvo diversa comunicazione, notizie riguardanti le attività svolte nell'ambito del presente Accordo.

6.3. Le spese per la gestione dell'orto sociale (compreso l'acquisto dei semi del prodotto da coltivare) saranno a carico del Comune di Arsoli.

6.4. Il ricavato risultante dalla vendita del prodotto coltivato nell'orto sociale sarà finalizzato all'acquisto di attrezzi per migliorare ed ampliare la coltivazione negli anni successivi.

Il presente atto, redatto su supporto informatico, è approvato e sottoscritto dalle parti.

Arsoli, li
Comune di Arsoli

Il Sindaco
Sig. Gabriele Caucci

Centro Sociale Anziani di Arsoli

Il Presidente
Sig. Fabrizio Proietti

PRO LOCO di Arsoli

Il Presidente
Arch. Chiara Bruni

Associazione amici della fagiolina di Arsoli

Il Presidente
Sig. Pietro Cerroni
